

AGRIGEP - ASSESSMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF AGRICULTURE AND LIFE SCIENCES UNIVERSITIES' FIRST GENDER EQUALITY PLANS IN WIDENING COUNTRIES

DO NOT MISS OUR FINAL CONFERENCE!

A banner for the AGRIGEP Final Conference. It features the AGRIGEP logo on the left, followed by the text "AGRIGEP Final Conference" and "Rooting Sustainable Change: Inclusive Gender Equality Plans in Agriculture and Life Sciences Universities in Central and Eastern Europe". Below this, it lists the date, location, format, and a URL. A QR code is on the right. The banner has a green border and a patterned background.

AGRIGEP Final Conference

Rooting Sustainable Change: Inclusive Gender Equality Plans in Agriculture and Life Sciences Universities in Central and Eastern Europe

Date: **25 September 2025**

Location: Czech University of Life Sciences, Prague

Format: In-person & hybrid

<https://agrigepeu.eu/agrigepe-final-conference/>

ABOUT THE AGRIGEP PROJECT

Discover the collaborative journey of change among six consortium partners; each higher education and research institution assesses their current Gender Equality Plan (GEP) implementation. Through a series of capacity-building activities, institutions strive to create a more inclusive and equitable environment. By crafting and enacting specialised GEPs for the fields of agriculture and life sciences, AGRIGEP aims to drive positive and lasting changes. Join us in this transformative initiative and be part of the journey towards a more balanced academic community.

COORDINATOR:

MATE – HUNGARIAN UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE AND LIFE SCIENCES

EC CONTRIBUTION: € 998, 237,50

DURATION: 36 MONTHS

START DATE: 1 JANUARY 2023

END DATE: 31 DECEMBER 2025

OUR GOALS:

1. Perform a responsible assessment of widening RPOs' current status on GEP implementation.
2. Improve capabilities through intensive capacity building.
3. Develop and implement agriculture and life-science targeted GEP with sectorial-specific measures and strategies.
4. Integrate GEP targets into the academic training materials of RPOs'.
5. Foster and support long-term structural changes of RPOs'.

THE CONSORTIUM

PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION NAME	STATUS	COUNTRY
Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE)	University	HU
Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU)	University	CZ
University of Primorska (UP)	University	SI
University Politecnica Catalunya (UPC)	University	ES
Yellow Window (YW)	SME	BE
Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE)	NGO	HU

MATE - The Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences

The Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) is the largest agriculture and environmental science-oriented higher education organization in Hungary, founded in 2021. Each campus of MATE has a long past and a rich history. Our Georgikon Faculty of Agricultural Sciences in Keszthely is the oldest regular agricultural higher education institution in Europe, which started its operation on July 1, 1797. Its legal predecessor was Szent István University, with decades-long existence. The University offers more than 50 diploma and degree courses as well as 52 MSc programs with a total of over 13000 students, and 14 Doctoral Schools with 756 PhD students.

DR. JULIANNA KOBOLÁK

„As a project coordinator, the driving force behind the application was to build a consortium that could appropriately support our local needs. Making the GEP plans mandatory has shown that the capacity gap in the GE field is significant in the CEE region, especially when the aim is to develop a GEP that provides a specific and efficient strategy addressing sector-specific needs for the institutions. We aimed to find both implementing partners and mentors with whom we can build long-term relationships; their commitment is an important driving force of the project.

The project is important not only for capacity-building purposes but also for laying the foundations for a long-term institutional change in organizational culture and strategic approach. It also connects us to an international network that would have been inaccessible without the AGRIGEP project. We at MATE are proud to receive this outstanding opportunity and could coordinate the AGRIGEP project.“

Agricultural Engineer, Senior Research Fellow Institute of Aquaculture and Environmental Safety of MATE as a AGRIGEP Team Lead at MATE

Project Coordinator

<https://en.uni-mate.hu/>

YW – Yellow Window

Yellow Window is a multi-disciplinary consultancy specializing in product, service and policy design, with considerable expertise in the fields of gender equality and social innovation. They have extensive experience in designing research methodologies, collecting and analysing complex and comprehensive data, drafting thorough and accessible reports communicating the research findings, and translating them into concrete (policy) recommendations.

DR. LUT MERGAERT

“At Yellow Window, we are committed to supporting institutional change for gender equality and inclusion in higher education and research. Building on our expertise, we help our university partners in the AGRIGEP project by providing tailored capacity-building activities, coaching and mentoring, to address their unique challenges and guide them through the process of GEP implementation in sometimes challenging contexts.

This role builds on our extensive experience in structural change projects such as GEECCO, SUPERA, GEARING-Roles and Gender-SMART, where we combine capacity-building with co-creation techniques to achieve sustainable and meaningful transformation beyond ticking the box of having a Gender Equality Plan. This is also why we developed a self-assessment tool for research and higher education institutions through which they can measure their capacity to implement institutional change for gender equality. It helps them identify their strengths and weaknesses, prioritise areas for improvement and communicate progress effectively with decision-making bodies and key stakeholders.”

Research Director and Senior Consultant at Yellow Window

Principal Investigator and coordinator of numerous policy support studies

Gender expert

<https://www.yellowwindow.com>

WHAT HAS HAPPENED IN THE PROJECT IN ITS 2ND YEAR?

SISTERS PROJECTS NETWORK

For the past year AGRIGEP has been part of a network of sister projects working together to share ideas and to support our common work. The network includes: AGRIGEP, SUPPORTER, NEXUS, GENDERSAFE, BUDGET-IN and STREAM IT.

DELIVERABLES: SHAPING THE FUTURE OF GENDER EQUALITY IN R&I

The AGRIGEP project focuses on creating a significant impact through its structured deliverables, each addressing key challenges in achieving gender equality in agriculture and life sciences. Below are the core deliverables already available:

1. D1. Data Management Plan (DMP) and IPR plan preparation (WP1)

A detailed DMP is prepared according to the project's specific needs, in line with CA and GA, to guarantee the FAIR data management and open science policy and to reach the proposed impacts of the project. The IPR and their protection measures are part of the DMP.

2. D2. DMP and IPR plan Revision 1 (WP1)

The DMP was revised at M18 and updated according to the consortium's needs in accordance with the GA and project progress, including the IPR monitoring.

3. D5. Policy Brief 1 (WP1)

A policy brief is prepared about the sectoral problems and needs, partially based on the capability and capacity assessments of the RPOs and mentor evaluations, focusing on widening countries and agriculture and life science RPOs.

4. D6. Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication (DEC) Plan (WP2)

Based on the proposal's plans, a detailed DEC plan is prepared to help the consortium reach the KERs and maximise the project's impact. This living document is updated continuously, and revised versions are published regularly.

Each deliverable supports AGRIGEP's vision of creating inclusive research-performing organizations that lead the way in gender equality in STEM fields. Visit the full **Deliverables section** for detailed insights and updates.

AGRIGEP EVENTS

UPC's visits: Gender and Teaching

Dr. Marta Peña and prof. Amaia Luca Garcia delivered a lecture on „Gender & Teaching: Inclusion of gender equality in Education“ through partnerships with the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, the University of Primorska Koper, and the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences Gödöllő. The lectures highlighted the relevance of addressing gender in teaching undergraduate and postgraduate programs, focusing on: equipping students to identify and challenge gender stereotypes.

Enhancing awareness of gender dynamics in learning environments.

Supporting talent management and career paths for women at the Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) A roundtable discussion on talent management in higher education took place at the Hungarian University of Agricultural and Life Sciences (MATE), with a special focus on talent management and support for women's career paths.

During the event, Zsófia Nagy-Vargha, Deputy State Secretary for Youth at the Ministry of Culture and Innovation, emphasised the importance of supporting talents. Csilla Fuszek, Director of the Budapest European Talent Centre, Dr Tamás Weiszburg, President of the National Council of Student Research Societies, OTDT (in Hungarian: Országos Tudományos Diákköri Tanács), and Enikő Szakos, an educational researcher at the Mathias Corvinus Collegium Foundation, provided insights into the various forms and opportunities of talent management in higher education and through preparatory programs.

GIRLS' DAY 2024

On April 24, 2025, MATE joined the international Girls' Day initiative, opening its campuses to young women interested in science, technology, engineering, and agriculture. The event aimed to inspire high school girls to explore academic and career opportunities in research, innovation, and sustainability. Participants had the chance to meet female researchers, visit laboratories, and take part in interactive workshops. Through personal stories and hands-on experiences, the program highlighted that women can thrive in traditionally male-dominated fields. With its commitment to equal opportunities, MATE continues to encourage the next generation of talented young women to pursue higher education and scientific careers.

Round Table of Fem2Forest

AGRIGEP project was presented together with GEP strategies of Czech University of Life Sciences Prague during hybrid event, Round Table of Forests in Women's Hands at CZU. We shared great insights during this event!

Summer school

The AGRIGEP Summer Meeting 2024, successfully brought together the consortium's six partner institutions for three days of productive collaboration and insightful discussions. Overall, the AGRIGEP Summer Meeting 2024 reinforced the consortium's dedication to embedding gender equality into the teaching and administrative frameworks of European universities. The event was a significant step forward in the project's mission to co-design and implement effective gender equality plans, ensuring a more inclusive and equitable future for higher education institutions.

On November 16th, the AGRIGEP project hosted a roundtable with four MATE professor women, highlighting their achievements in science and teaching as well as their career journeys. The discussion touched on equal opportunities, the challenges of building a long-term academic career, and the role of universities in attracting and retaining students. The professors emphasized the importance of family, supportive colleagues, and strong role models, while also underlining communication, empathy, and personalized career support. Despite challenges and limited recognition, they agreed their work is deeply rewarding. The light-hearted conversation revealed inspiring personal stories, showing these professors as role models not only in science but also in work-life balance. The next session will feature young women entrepreneurs sharing their perspectives on innovation and career success.

Day of Women and Girls in Science

In 2024, the Women in Science Award of Excellence of the Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE) was presented for the eleventh time on the occasion of the International Women’s Day, to honour the most outstanding women researchers in their field, under the auspices of the Hungarian National Commission for UNESCO. This year’s winners of the Award of Excellence are researching cancer cells and climate change – are role models who are inspiring the next generation.

Day of Women and Girls in Science

On April 14, 2025, the Association of Hungarian Women in Science (NaTE) honoured outstanding women who not only lead in their fields – but also inspire.

These awards shine a light on diverse scientific roles and the people behind them – from lab to classroom – proving that science thrives on collaboration, support, and passion.

MIC 2024 conference at the University of Trento in Italy

MCYR 2024 conference at CZU, FTA, Prague

through the poster presentation, participants explored how the integration of gender perspectives can enhance the quality of research in reproductive biotechnology. The discussions that followed created opportunities for future collaborations between the AGRIGEP team and other international institutions working toward shared goals.

RESET Conference

Porto: Agrigep was part of the **WeResEt Final Conference**, a gathering of research institutions and policymakers from across Europe. This event was of utmost importance to AGRIGEP as it aligned with the WeResEt initiative's mission of „resetting“ research systems to be more equitable and inclusive.

Second Symposium on Gender Equality for an Inclusive University and Society at the Faculty of management, University of Primorska brought together experts, scholars, and stakeholders to address critical topics, such as gender equality, the intersectionality of identity, and the role of universities in fostering inclusive societies on November 15. During the symposium consortium participated in Roundtable with stakeholders.

On 13-14 November 2024, **AGRIGEP Annual Meeting** took place in Slovenia, bringing all consortium members together.

PLEDGE FOR

#ZERO TOLERANCE

Take a stand against ANY form of gender-based violence in research and academia

Funded by the European Union

International Day of Rural Women

During **International Day for the Elimination of Violence Against Women** (November 25), AGRI-GEP joined pledge for zero tolerance organised by GenderSAFE and GENDERACTIONplus projects on their online campaign.

We celebrated **International Day of Rural Women** with successful photo challenge through the social media connecting sister projects and individuals together by sharing their picture regarding topic of: cultivating food for all.

Dr. **Jana Mazancová** as a keynote speaker at **Seed Summit 2024** delivering presentation: Gender Aspects of the Agri-food during panel addresses gender disparities in access to resources such as land, finance, and education. It advocates for policies and programs that promote women’s participation and leadership in agriculture and agri-food businesses. Additionally, it raises awareness of women’s contributions to agriculture and the importance of recognizing and valuing their work. The panel also emphasizes the need for training and capacity-building opportunities to empower women farmers and entrepreneurs.

Guiding questions to frame the discussion during the online engagement webinar **Integrating a Feminist Perspective in Research Projects**. The webinar took place on 12 December 2024.

Online engagement webinar

INTEGRATING A FEMINIST PERSPECTIVE IN RESEARCH PROJECTS

14h Welcome to the session

Introduction of the projects reflecting on the following:

- Why and for what purpose was the project created?
- What do we do? Main activities and how we do organize
- How do we position our research (political, theoretical framework, methodology, action, etc.)?
- Why do you 'use'/stand with a feminists/gender perspective?

Shared reflection on conducting feminist/gender research (group work)

15h Break

15:15h Shared reflection on conducting feminist/gender research (plenary)

16h Closing

SUPPORTER's final conference on Advancing Gender Equality Plans in Widening higher education institutions!

Jana Mazancova delivered insights on how to tailor GEPs in higher education institutions to specific ecosystems at the sister project SUPPORTER's final conference held on 4–5 July 2025 in Prague.

There were two different workshops organised as part of the visit, 14-15 January, Gödöllő Hungary. The one focusing on Gender perspective on the Climate change and Circular Economy – specifically for PhD students and international students, and a second workshop on gender in research: how to integrate the gender perspective into research topics – for PI-s.

Training materials for employees and students were developed under the lead of Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC, Barcelona). These resources focus on three core themes: the integration of the gender dimension in teaching, the inclusion of the gender dimension in research, and the prevention of gender-based violence and sexual harassment. While similar initiatives exist, the report highlights how AGRIGEP's approach is shaped by its specific audiences, timelines, and resources. The materials were originally created in English and subsequently translated into Hungarian, Czech, and Slovenian, supporting their wider use across partner institutions. Training materials are publicly available at AGRIGEP websites: [Training materials - Agrigep](#).

TRAINING MATERIALS FOR EMPLOYEES & STUDENTS

Inclusion of the gender dimension in teaching

Inclusion of the gender dimension in research

Gender-based violence and sexual harassment

AGRIGEP Team Presented at the 30th ESRS Congress in Riga

Members of the AGRIGEP team from the Czech University of Life Sciences Prague (CZU) took part in the 30th Congress of the European Society for Rural Sociology (ESRS), which was held in Riga, Latvia, from 7 to 11 July 2025 under the theme Navigating rural transitions: Exploring liveable futures.

During the event, the team contributed to the working group Reflecting on Inclusive Research Practices in Rural Context with a presentation of their paper entitled „Gender Inclusiveness in Research at Life Science Universities.“ The paper shared selected findings from the AGRIGEP project and sparked a fruitful discussion on institutional change and gender-sensitive research environments in higher education.

SUCCESSFUL COMPLETION OF SISTER PROJECTS' WEBINAR SERIES ON GENDER EQUALITY

The AGRIGEP project, in collaboration with six Horizon Europe sister projects – GENDERSAFE, SUPPORTER, NEXUS, BUDGET IT, GENDERACTION+, and STREAM IT – successfully concluded a free monthly webinar series on gender equality in higher education and research institutions. The series, which ran from September 2024 to 20 May 2025, provided valuable insights and practical knowledge aimed at promoting gender equality and inclusivity across the academic sector. The AGRIGEP project coordinated the series, and each sister project hosted a webinar, mobilising their own network and sharing their experiences, best practices or even barriers they faced.

The webinars covered a broad range of timely and critical topics, many of which are at the forefront of the sister project activities. The webinar series featured the following eight topics:

- Effective Crisis Communication Management: Navigating Gender-Based Violence in Higher Education – hosted by GENDERSAFE
- Stakeholder Mapping and Engagement for GEP Implementation: Experiences from CEE Universities – hosted by AGRIGEP
- Embedding Inclusivity in Communication: The Power of Words and Visuals – hosted by SUPPORTER
- The Impact of Anti-Gender Discourses and Politics on Academic and Research Organisations – hosted by NEXUS
- Gender Budgeting: A Practical Application – hosted by BUDGET IT
- Relevance of Monitoring for Effective Gender Equality Policy Implementation in ERA – hosted by GenderAction +
- Advancing Gender Equality in STEAM Higher Education: Exploring Challenges, Opportunities, and Institutional Strategies – hosted by STREAM IT
- Revisiting AI Research and Teaching: Integrating Gender and Intersectional Perspectives – hosted by NEXUS

Each session attracted participants from diverse backgrounds, fostering rich discussions and the sharing of best practices. The series enabled institutions to learn from experts and peers, helping to strengthen their Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and policies.

The entire series was offered free of charge, with registration open to anyone interested in advancing gender equality in research and higher education.

For more information about the webinar recordings and related resources, please visit the AGRIGEP website at agrigeu.eu/ge-webinars.

UPCOMING EVENTS

AGRIGEP Final Conference

Project AGRIGEP: NO. 101094158

Rooting Sustainable Change: Inclusive Gender Equality Plans in Agriculture and Life Sciences Universities in Central and Eastern Europe

25 September 2025
Czech University of Life Sciences Prague

Why Attend?

- Diverse perspectives from academia, policy & practice
- Actionable insights from real GEP implementation
- Future pathways for inclusion in agri & life sciences
- Input into gender-responsive policy recommendations

Registration

Highlights

- Policy Roundtable: Advancing Gender Equality in Academia for Sustainability, Excellence, Competitiveness and Economic Growth in Europe
- Keynote: Marcela Linková on shifting from formal compliance to true commitment
- Panel discussion 1: GEP 1.0 lessons & vision for GEP 2.0;
- Panel discussion 2: Sectoral strategies in agriculture & life sciences
- Poster Pitches: Spotlight on student and sister projects
- Call to Action: Driving inclusive transformation across European universities

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

CONFERENCE AIMS

The AGRIGEP Final Conference aims to **reflect on and synthesise the experiences gained during the implementation of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)** in agricultural and life sciences higher education institutions (HEIs) across Central and Eastern Europe. As a culmination of the three-year project, the event **brings together educators, policymakers, researchers, students, and practitioners to identify persisting challenges and explore future pathways** for sustainable institutional transformation.

With a sectoral focus on agrifood and natural resource management, the conference places **gender equality at the heart of innovation, competitiveness, and academic excellence**. The event will showcase practical examples, discuss lessons learned, and explore stakeholder engagement strategies that drive real change. Insights from sister projects and EU-level policy experts will inform policy recommendations and empower stakeholders to create inclusive academic and professional environments.

CONFERENCE AGENDA

9:00 Registration

9:30 Opening Session

Prof. Michal Lošťák, Vice-rector, Czech University of Life Sciences

Julianna Kobolák, Senior Researcher, Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences, AGRIGEP project coordinator

Katharina Buse, Project Officer, European Research Executive Agency

10:00 Keynote Speech

Marcela Linková, Head of the Centre for Gender and Science at the Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Member State Co-Chair of the ERA Forum Sub-group on Inclusive Gender Equality, an advisory body to the European Commission.

10.30 Coffee Break

10.50 Policy Round Table: Advancing Gender Equality in Academia for Sustainability, Excellence, Competitiveness and Economic Growth in Europe

Moderator: Maxime Forest, Gender and Policy Design Expert, Yellow Window, Senior Lecturer and Research Associate at Sciences Po (OFCE, Urban School)

Speakers:

Adéla Gjuričová, Director of the Institute of Contemporary History of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Vice-Chair of the Research, Development and Innovation Council of the Czech Government

Katalin Tardos, Senior Researcher of the HUN-REN Centre for Social Sciences, Institute for Sociology, Hungary

Hana Tenglerová, Policy Officer, DG Research & Innovation, Unit D4 - Democracy, Equality & Culture - Gender Sector

Gita Zadnikar, Policy Officer, Slovenian Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation

12.15 Lunch break

13.15 Panel Discussion 1: Shaping gender equality in academia: Lessons from GEP 1.0 and visions for GEP 2.0

Moderator: **Panagiota Polykarpou**, Consultant for Equality, Diversity and Inclusion, Yellow Window

Panellists:

Štefan Bojnec, Professor of Economics and Head of the Department of Economics at the Faculty of Management, University of Primorska

Sara Clavero, project NEXUS, Senior Researcher and Deputy Director RINCE (AIB Research Centre for Inclusive and Equitable Cultures) at TU Dublin EDI

Lenka Henebergová, project SUPPORTER, Senior Researcher, Vice-dean for internationalisation at Charles University in Prague

Julianna Kobolák, Coordinator of AGRIGEP; Senior Research fellow at Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE), Hungary

Michal Lošťák, Professor of Sociology, Vice rector and Head of the Department of Humanities at the Faculty of Economy and Management, Czech University of Life Sciences

Katalin Oborni, Senior Project Manager at HÉTFA's Division of International Cooperation, coordinates the RE-FEM and STREAM IT projects, Gender Officer for the COST Action project PROFEEDBACK

14.30 Poster Pitch session with coffee

15.45 Panel Discussion 2: Advancing gender equality in Agriculture and Life Sciences

Opening presentation: **Veronika Paksi**, research fellow at the Institute for Sociology, Centre for Social Sciences (Hungarian Academy of Sciences Centre of Excellence)

Moderator: **Katalin Tardos**, Senior Researcher of the HUN-REN Centre for Social Sciences, Institute for Sociology

Panellists:

Maura Farrell, FLIARA project, Senior Lecturer, School of Geography and Archaeology, National University of Ireland, Galway

Jana Mazancová, AGRIGEP project, Senior Researcher at the Department of Sustainable Technology, Faculty of Tropical AgriSciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague

Petra Palátová, Fem2forests project, Lecturer and researcher at the Faculty of Forestry and Wood Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences in Prague

Dimitris Tsaltas, Professor and Director of Agricultural Microbiology and Biotechnology Laboratory, Head of Department of Agricultural Sciences, Biotechnology and Food Science at the Cyprus University of Technology

17.00 Final Remarks

17.15 Closure of the conference

EVENT	PLACE & DATE
Annual Meeting: 23. – 24. 9. 2025	Prague

PUBLICATIONS:

New AGRIGEP Scientific Publication Highlights Gender Equality Barriers in Central European Agriculture and Life Sciences Universities

A new scientific publication was developed within AGRIGEP project, shedding light on gender equality barriers in agriculture and life sciences across universities in Central and Eastern Europe.

Title: Gender Equality Barriers in Agriculture and Life Sciences in Central European Universities

Authors: Veronika Paksi, Katalin Tardos, Judit Takács, Csilla Judit Suhajda, Jana Mazancová, Štefan Bojnec, Julianna Kobilák

[Full text and free PDF download HERE.](#)

WHAT IS THE STUDY ABOUT?

While much attention has been paid to gender inequality in STEM fields, this study explores the often-overlooked barriers faced by women in the agriculture and life sciences fields, which are often seen as gender-balanced. Through nine focus groups involving 82 participants from Czech, Hungarian, and Slovenian universities, the research highlights how gendered obstacles persist across academia, particularly in recruitment, promotion, work-life balance, leadership, and fieldwork conditions.

Key findings include:

- Persistent gender stereotypes in education and career choices
- Structural barriers in recruitment and promotion practices
- Underrepresentation of women in leadership
- Additional gendered challenges tied to laboratory and fieldwork
- The need for context-sensitive, tailor-made Gender Equality Plans (GEPs)

This study not only contributes to academic debate but also provides practical recommendations for updating institutional GEPs and promoting more inclusive university environments.

This publication is part of the broader effort to support evidence-based policymaking and institutional reform under our project's mission to advance gender equality in research and higher education.

Read and share the article: Paksi, V., Tardos, K., Takács, J., Suhajda, C., Mazancová, J., Bojnec, Š., & Kobilák, J. (2025). Gender Equality Barriers in Agriculture and Life Sciences in Central European Universities. *Social Inclusion*, 13, Article 10086. [ARTICLE HERE.](#)

Read and share the thematic issue [‘Gender Equality Plans in European Research Performing Organisations’](#) edited by Katalin Tardos, Veronika Paksi, Judit Takács and Rita Bencivenga. *Social Inclusion*, 13, 2025.

HOW TO REACH US:

AGRIGEP Coordination Office: for more information about AGRIGEP project, please contact the coordination team from Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE).

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